

On the Development of CSFH MEMS-Technology based Micro Robots

Matteo Verotti
*Department of Mechanical, Energy,
Management and Transportation Engineering
University of Genoa
Genoa, Italy
matteo.verotti@unige.it*

Nicola Pio Belfiore
*Dept. of Engineering
University of Roma Tre
Rome, Italy
nicolapio.belfiore@uniroma3.it*

Abstract—The demand of micromanipulation has been increasing, during the last decades, in several fields of applications, including microelectronics, minimal invasive surgery, and aerospace. This paper illustrates how a recently developed flexure hinge gave rise to some developments in the fields of micromanipulation and how it could be used for the design of new concept micro robots.

Index Terms—Mechanism Design, Micro/Nano Robots, Space Robotics and Automation, Surgical Robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Devices miniaturization received a great impulse thanks to the progress in microelectronic fabrication, which lead to the development of Micro Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS). Nowadays, MEMS devices have already found significant applications in many sectors, including the biomedical field [1], [2].

However, serious problems limited the use of MEMS-Technology for developing micro mechanisms and micro robots. Among them, actuation and mobility were (and still are) real challenges to designers.

Actuation of microsystems remains a not completely solved problem, mainly because the scaling effects change the paradigms used in classical robotics. For example, inertial and electromagnetic forces, which are the governing forces at the macro scale, become much less effective than the surface forces, which increase their influence on the microsystem dynamics [3].

The problem of mobility is even more complicated. In fact, most of the MEMS Technology processes are basically planar process of micro-machining, based on photolithography. Unfortunately, planar processes introduce a technical difficulty in machining or assembly revolute joints which are the most widely used kinematic pairs in mechanisms and robotics. To solve this problem a large variety of flexure hinges have been proposed, based on material elasticity [4].

The main problem with flexure hinges consists in the lack of any guarantee that the center $P_{i,j}$ of the relative rotation between any two adjacent bodies i and j will stay constantly at a certain position, which makes the overall motion very difficult to be calculated or simulated. For this reason, the Conjugate Surface Flexure Hinge (CSFH) has been introduced

in 2009 [5], in order to guarantee that the simultaneous action of a portion of conjugate surfaces makes the position of $P_{i,j}$ practically unchanged, within the limits of the conjugate surfaces gap.

Fig. 1. A view of the CSFH and the companion rotary comb drive, where C_1 and C_2 are the anchored and mobile parts that are connected together by means of the flexible curved beam B_C and constrained by the conjugate surfaces S_C , the actuation being provided by the fixed and mobile series of fingers F_1 and F_2 of the comb drive.

The CSFH hinge, as illustrated in Figure 1, is based on the simultaneous action of a pair of conjugate surfaces S_C and a flexible curved beam B_C . Its basic working principle relies on

the circumstance that the center of the conjugate profiles S_C on a plane is coincident with the center of the elastic weights of the curved beam B_C [6]. Further details about the elastic behavior of the circular arc beam have been provided in Refs. [7], [8].

II. THE JOINT REPLACEMENT METHOD

The adoption of the CSFH allows designers to apply the joint replacement method with high accuracy.

The problem of synthesis consists in finding a new compliant mechanism that is able to cope with the assigned functional requirements or tasks. In this case, the joint replacement method relies on two basic steps: (i) the synthesis of a mechanism with ordinary kinematic pairs and (ii) the construction of a compliant mechanism based on the system obtained in the previous step. A recent example of synthesis of a MEMS Technology based microsystem has been described in [9].

The problem of analysis consists in studying the kinematic, functional or task characteristics of a given mechanism. In this case the two before mentioned steps are simply reversed, since an ordinary mechanism is obtained from the given compliant mechanism and then the ordinary kinematic analysis is applied.

Fig. 2. Application of the joint replacement method: the compliant manipulator (a) and the corresponding pseudo-rigid body model (b); the CSFHs S_1 , S_2 , S_3 are replaced by the revolute joints R_1 , R_2 and R_3 , respectively.)

Figure 2 shows an example of joint replacement method applied to a RRR serial plane microrobot. The mechanism represented in Figure 2 (b) is the pseudo-rigid body model (PRBM) corresponding to the compliant mechanism represented in Figure 2 (a).

Considering the design of a new microsystem, the first stage consists of the synthesis of an ordinary mechanism, as the one depicted in Figure 2. (b). Then, the joint replacement method is applied to build the system represented in Figure 2 (a).

In the analysis of an existing microsystem, as the one represented in Figure 2 (a), the first step consists in obtaining its corresponding PRBM, as in Figure 2 (b), and then the kinematic analysis is applied to the found PRBM.

III. THE VARIETY OF TOPOLOGIES POTENTIALLY USED IN MICRO ROBOTICS

The design procedure which makes use of the joint replacement method offers several advantages, such as the compatibility with the planar fabrication method and the possibility of achieving

- multi-hinge structures;
- parallel structures (multi-loops);
- multi degrees of freedom (DoFs).

The above mentioned method has been applied to design several micro devices that have been fabricated by means of the Deep Reactive-Ion Etching (D-RIE) process [10]. For example, microgrippers [11] and micro platforms [12] have been recently built and tested also in operational conditions [13].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The Research Unit "Micro Nano Facility" of the Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, Italy, is gratefully acknowledged for the DRIE fabrication of several samples of microgrippers embedding the CSFH hinge.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Bogue, "Recent developments in MEMS sensors: A review of applications, markets and technologies," *Sensor Review*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 300–304, 2013.
- [2] A. Nisar, N. Afzulpurkar, B. Mahaisavariya, and A. Tuantranont, "Mems-based micropumps in drug delivery and biomedical applications," *Sensors and Actuators, B: Chemical*, vol. 130, no. 2, pp. 917–942, 2008.
- [3] N. P. Belfiore (Ed.), *Micromanipulation. Special Issue of Actuators*, Various authors, Ed. MDPI Books Publishing Open Access Books and Series, 2018, ISBN 978-3-03897-503-8 (Pbk); ISBN 978-3-03897-504-5 (PDF), Free Download at <https://www.mdpi.com/books/pdfview/book/1070>.
- [4] N. Lobontiu, *Compliant mechanisms: Design of flexure hinges*, 1st Edition, Ed. CRC Press, 2002.
- [5] N. P. Belfiore, M. Scaccia, F. Ianniello, and M. Presta, "Selective compliance hinge," Italy, extended to Patent World Intellectual Property Organization, WO 2009/034 551 A1, Int. Appl. No. PCT/IB2008/053 697, Publ. Date March, 19th, 2009 (extended US 8,191,204 B2, Jun.5, 2012), 2009.
- [6] M. Verotti, R. Crescenzi, M. Balucani, and N. P. Belfiore, "Mems-based conjugate surfaces flexure hinge," *Journal of Mechanical Design, Transactions of the ASME*, vol. 137, no. 1, 2015.
- [7] M. Verotti, "Analysis of the center of rotation in primitive flexures: Uniform cantilever beams with constant curvature," *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 97, pp. 29–50, 2016.
- [8] —, "Effect of initial curvature in uniform flexures on position accuracy," *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 119, pp. 106–118, 2018.
- [9] M. Verotti, A. Dochshanov, and N. P. Belfiore, "Compliance synthesis of csfh mems-based microgrippers," *Journal of Mechanical Design, Transactions of the ASME*, vol. 139, no. 2, 2017.
- [10] A. Bagolini, S. Ronchin, P. Bellutti, M. Chistè, M. Verotti, and N. P. Belfiore, "Fabrication of novel mems microgrippers by deep reactive ion etching with metal hard mask," *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 926–934, 2017.
- [11] C. Potrich, L. Lunelli, A. Bagolini, P. Bellutti, C. Pederzolli, M. Verotti, and N. P. Belfiore, "Innovative silicon microgrippers for biomedical applications: Design, mechanical simulation and evaluation of protein fouling," *Actuators*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2018.
- [12] M. Verotti, A. Bagolini, P. Bellutti, and N. P. Belfiore, "Design and validation of a single-soi-wafer 4-dof crawling microgripper," *Micromachines*, vol. 10, no. 6, 2019.
- [13] F. Vurchio, P. Ursi, A. Buzzin, A. Veroli, A. Scorza, M. Verotti, S. A. Sciuto, and N. P. Belfiore, "Grasping and releasing agarose micro beads in water drops," *Micromachines*, vol. 10, no. 7, 2019.